

Investigation of the amino acid derivatives and small peptides profile in culinary bases

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Abstract

Taste is an important aspect affecting the palatability of food. As such, it is essential to determine responsible compounds influencing taste perception. In the savoury area, monosodium glutamate (MSG) and sodium chloride (NaCl) are the predominant compounds responsible for taste attributes “umami” and “salty”, respectively, but both ingredients are sometimes avoided by consumers for various reasons. Although numerous alternative compounds are reported in literature as having taste modulating activity, identification and quantification is often restricted to only specific food products and compound classes. Data on concentration of described taste modulating substances in a wide range of raw materials is limited and a systematic correlation with the taste perception of the final products is lacking. Therefore, this study was conducted to 1) gain a first insight into the role of previously described compounds with umami, salty or kokumi activity in savoury applications and 2) to establish their potential to increase the taste complexity beyond MSG and NaCl. To fulfil this demand, an LC-qTOF-MS method was developed allowing the simultaneous quantification of various small peptides and amino acid derivatives known to have taste modulating activity in the savoury area. The method was validated as a semi-quantitative screening method for a large number of compounds and the selected components were quantified in several food ingredients commonly used in savoury applications.

Keywords: taste, savoury food, small peptides, amino acid derivatives, LC-qTOF-MS

Introduction

There is growing interest to discover new compounds that improve savoury taste quality besides L-glutamate and sodium chloride and, especially, find natural sources containing these components. Many have already been reported in literature including umami tasting as well as umami and salty increasing compounds. Additionally, another taste modulating activity, kokumi, has gained more attention and several responsible compounds with this activity have been identified. These molecules are reported to increase mouthfulness, thickness, complexity, and taste continuity [1-3]. Compounds that can impact the savoury taste belong to various chemical classes, seven of which are displayed in Figure 1. However, quantitative data on these numerous compounds in foods is limited. Therefore, in this work a Liquid Chromatography-Quadrupole Time-of-Flight-Mass Spectrometry (LC-qTOF-MS) multi-method was developed to move towards establishing the potential of these molecules to increase taste complexity as well as enable their in-situ generation.

Figure 1: Compound classes that are reported to influence savoury taste and were analysed in the developed multi-method.

Experimental

Samples

The analysed samples were ingredients commonly used in savoury applications including commercial yeast extracts, kitchen-scale cooking bases, lab-scale hydrolysed vegetable mixtures and mushrooms, lab-scale wheat gluten hydrolysates and fermented wheat gluten. Vegetable, mushroom, and wheat gluten hydrolysates were prepared by hydrolysis using different peptidases.

Sensory evaluation

Hydrolysed and fermented wheat gluten samples were comparatively evaluated to a binary mixture of NaCl and MSG by a trained sensory panel with and without nose-clip. For the comparative analysis, NaCl and MSG concentrations of samples and references were adjusted to the same level in two sets, Set 1 and Set 2 (low and high MSG concentration).

Sample Extraction

Samples were extracted with an aqueous formic acid solution (0.1 %) for 30 min at 25 °C. The resulting mixture was centrifuged, the supernatant filtered through a membrane filter and diluted 1:1 with acetonitrile. After another centrifugation step, the supernatant was analysed by sequential window acquisition of all theoretical fragment ion–mass spectrometry (SWATH-MS).

LC-ESI⁺-SWATH-MS analysis

The extracted samples were analysed on a Sciex TripleTOF 5600+ System. Liquid chromatographic separation was achieved on an Agilent 1260 Infinity system with a Waters ACQUITY UPLC BEH Amide Column (130Å, 1.7 µm, 2.1 mm x 150 mm) using mobile phases A (H₂O/ACN-90/10; 20 mM ammonium formate, pH 2.8) and B (H₂O/ACN-10/90; 20 mM ammonium formate, pH 2.8) by applying gradient elution. MS analysis was done in SWATH mode with a TOF survey scan (*m/z* 50-1250, 80 ms) followed by 10 product ion scans with variable Q1 isolation windows from *m/z* 50 to 1250 with an overlap of 1 Da. Product ion spectra were accumulated in high-sensitivity mode for 70 ms using DP of 70 V, CE of 35 V, and CES of 15 V. Quantification was achieved by the standard addition method.

Amino acid and ribonucleotide analysis

The content of free amino acids and ribonucleotides of the five wheat gluten samples evaluated by a sensory panel were determined by LC-UV analysis.

Results and discussion

Reported compounds with savoury taste influencing activity belong to various chemical classes (see Figure 1) and can therefore represent a challenge for simultaneous analysis in a multi-method. Despite gaining selectivity by applying high-resolution mass spectrometry with a qTOF-MS, many of the analytes have the same molecular weight and needed to be chromatographically separated. The optimized method enabled good separation of most analytes to satisfy selective quantification (chromatogram see Figure 2).

Figure 2: LC-chromatogram of a standard solution containing all analytes.

A good LC separation along with SWATH-MS analysis and High-Resolution (HR)-MS of the TOF scan allowed to obtain HR-MS/MS spectra for all detected compounds (13 amino acid derivatives, 15 α -glutamyl-peptides, 18 γ -glutamyl-peptides, 13 arginyl-peptides, five cysteine derivatives, 15 Amadori compounds and 16 pyroglutamyl-peptides). In the very complex food matrices evaluated interferences in the TOF scan could often be observed which hamper secure identification and quantification. SWATH-MS analysis using MS or MS/MS acquisition for quantification enabled the determination of the whole range of analysed compounds.

The developed method was validated with two representative matrices, vegetable mixture (VM) and hydrolysed wheat gluten (WG). Limit of quantification was determined as the concentration for which signal-to-noise ratios were above 10. They varied per compound group, were predominantly lower than 0.1 µg/mL and below known taste thresholds for the respective compounds. Recovery and precision of the method for the analysed compounds are summarised in Figure 3 and showed recovery values between 70 and 120 % and precision values predominantly below 20 %. The linearity range was also applicable to the concentrations quantified in the analysed samples.

Figure 3: Box-Plots for recovery and precision values for vegetable mixture (VM) and hydrolysed wheat gluten (WG) samples of all analysed compounds (RSDr: intra-day precision; RSDr: inter-day precision).

Subsequently, the developed method was applied to a range of different samples and determined quantities of the various compounds are summarised as a heatmap in Figure 4. It could be observed that amino acid derivatives were only present in fermented wheat gluten as well as yeast extracts, in line with their reported generation during fermentation [3]. Yeast extracts generally showed a relatively high quantity of small peptides compared to the other samples. Cysteine derivatives analysed could only be detected in vegetable hydrolysates containing onion and garlic. Mushroom samples showed high amounts of α -glutamyl-peptides compared to the other hydrolysates investigated. It could be observed that different enzyme preparations displayed a varied peptide profile even though the same substrate (wheat gluten) was used. Enzyme preparation 1 (Enz 1) showed a significant increase of γ -glutamyl-peptides, whereas with enzyme preparation 2 (Enz 2) almost none could be detected. This observation suggests a side activity to peptide hydrolysis that generates γ -glutamyl-peptides in Enz 1. Pyroglutamyl peptides are present in high amounts in wheat gluten samples. This could be explained by the high concentration of glutamine in wheat gluten, as pyroglutamyl peptides can also be formed from glutaminyl peptides [3]. Further optimization of the food process based on these observations can be performed as clearly sample discrimination was achieved.

Figure 4: Hierarchical cluster analysis and heat map visualization of samples (rows) and display of the quantified compounds (columns).

Wheat gluten samples were evaluated by a sensory panel with and without nose-clip, the former to focus primarily on taste. In order to gain a first insight into the taste profile that extends beyond MSG and NaCl, their corresponding concentrations were determined and adjusted in all samples to the same value in Set 1 and Set 2

with low and high MSG concentration, respectively. In a comparative analysis, it was observed that all the samples showed a significant increase in umami and/or salty taste perception compared to the reference (Figure 5). Therefore, sensory analysis indicated further compounds present in the samples that influence (additive, synergistic and/or enhancing effects) taste perception. Specifically, an increase of umami and salty tastes as well as an increase in umami aftertaste and in total time-intensity of taste perception were observed. This effect was still perceivable even at a higher concentration of MSG (Set 2). The lack of ribonucleotides in these samples can exclude their contribution to the observed increase in taste perception, which suggest other responsible compounds to be present [1]. Further sensory and analytical experiments are needed to determine which compound(s) are responsible for the increase in the mentioned taste profiles.

Figure 5: Comparative taste profile analyses on a scale of 0-10 against reference which was set to a value of 0. Only significant differences to the reference are shown. FL: Flavour determined with nose-clip; AF: Aftertaste – intensity after set time with nose-clip; Time-intensity: Taste-intensity after set time with nose-clip; MF: Mouthfeel; Salivation: Increased salivation; *MF values determined without nose-clip.

Conclusion

An LC-SWATH-MS multi-method was developed to simultaneously quantify a total of 95 compounds belonging to the chemical classes of small peptides and amino acid derivatives that have been reported to influence the savoury taste perception. The method was successfully applied to various culinary bases that are commonly used in savoury applications, and, therefore fulfilled its role as a semi-quantitative screening multi-method for seven different compound classes with the possibility to easily include a higher number of compounds. This analytical tool can be used to move towards determining the full profile of taste compounds in complex samples in a fast and simple manner. Generated data could be used for a more data-driven recipe generation process and selection of ingredients to achieve the desired taste profile. Sensory analysis confirmed the possibility to increase taste complexity beyond salt and MSG. Furthermore, this method can also offer the opportunity to monitor process optimization for the generation of reported taste influencing compounds in the savoury area. Therefore, the developed LC-qTOF-MS multi-method represents a versatile tool for taste improvement.

References

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